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Improving Medication Safety in an Inpatient Setting

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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By

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ABSTRACT

At a community hospital in Southern California, medications were administered 168,117 times in 2016. Only 25 medication administration errors were reported with only five errors reported by nurses. The five reporting nurses did so due to patients experiencing problems/adverse reactions. Interviews with nurses indicated that they perceived the reporting process as burdensome and time-consuming. This situation suggests under-reporting of medication errors, in particular, *near miss* errors. Medication errors are also monitored closely by The Joint Commission (TJC), the State of California, and the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid (CMS), so active reporting and monitoring is essential for successful accreditation by TJC and compliance with State and Federal requirements.

The purpose of this project is to improve the hospital's medication error reporting process in order to enhance reporting of all types of medication errors. The following objectives guided the work: (a) refine medication error reporting processes; (b) educate nurses and pharmacists regarding medication error definitions and reporting criteria; (c) develop strategies to address reporting accountability for medication errors made by nurses; (d) evaluate nurse response to the changes and (e) monitor reporting medication errors.

A literature search supported introduction of three interventions that might improve hospital medication safety. The first is to implement education and training to

bridge knowledge gaps related to a standardized medication error reporting protocol. The second is to improve the logistics and rationale of the reporting system to reduce staff burden. Last is to improve feedback such that nurses are aware of changes made that aim at error resolution. All activities should be done within a non-punitive environment where nurses understand the meaning of reporting to promote patient safety and are not afraid of individual blame. Framed in an adapted Safety Action and Information Feedback from Incident Reporting (SAIFIR) framework (Benn et al., 2009), this project proposed to pilot changes on a 62-bed medical-surgical/telemetry unit where 50% of the nursing staff (40 nurses) has less than three years of acute hospital experience.

In this ongoing project, policies were reviewed, revised and approved in November 2018. A 4-week staff education program was held during February 2018 along with education for new staff hires with emphasis of a no individual blame culture. The Verge Solution incident reporting software reference guide was developed to assist staff to reduce reporting time. The reference guide was introduced to staff and made available in the unit's resource binder. The audit tool was reviewed and revised with input from charge nurses. The audit was implemented starting in February 2018. The strategies to enhance communication to nurses about medication errors and changes in policies or procedures began with daily huddles on the pilot unit; nurses were receptive to this. The generic email acknowledgment to staff that will be sent once an incident report is received was approved by the CNO in January 2018. Critical to this project has been direct involvement with the director of pharmacy, who is accountable for medication error reporting for the hospital.

This quality improvement project is ongoing, and no results are available as of completion of this project. This project requires continuous monitoring using the metrics in the evaluation plan, with revisions of the process as needed. The project lead will informally collect staff feedback regarding the medication error reporting process. The plan is that the project lead and DoP will meet bi-weekly and as needed to review medication error reports. The project lead will analyze the AHRQ Patient Safety Culture survey results collected during the August 2018 skills fair. The 2018 results will be compared to those from 2016 and 2017 to identify changes in staff perception of medication safety; specifically, whether they perceived receipt of feedback about changes put into place based on event reports and being informed about errors that happen on their unit.

Medication errors can happen at any step during the medication administration process. This project translates evidence-based strategies for enhancing medication error reporting in hospital nursing practice and demonstrates the necessary collaboration across disciplines when medication error reporting changes are made. Improving medication safety will not only assist in reducing errors but, more importantly, will create staff awareness necessary to provide safe care.

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INTRODUCTION

Medication administration in hospitals is a multi-step process that consists of prescribing, transcribing, dispensing, and administering drugs, followed by monitoring patient responses. An error can happen at any step during this process (Kavanagh, 2017). A medication error refers to an error at any time between a provider prescribing a medication to the period of monitoring the patient's response post administration (National Coordinating Council of Medication Error Reporting and Prevention [NCCMERP], 2017). Medication errors can include wrong diagnosis, wrong medication, wrong dosage, wrong frequency, wrong time, and failure to give medication. Medication errors can lead to patient harm, yet most are preventable (National Coordinating Council of Medication Error Reporting and Prevention [NCCMERP], 2017). In California, hospitals are mandated by the California Department of Public Health (CDPH) to report medication errors internally as part of the Senate Bill medication safety reprogram ("Alquist health facilities: reporting and inspection requirements, Senate Bill 1301," 2006).

Since 2003, medication safety has been one of The Joint Commission's (TJC) National Patient Safety Goals. Strategies have been developed to minimize the risk of error; these include computerized provider order entry, medication reconciliation, clinical pharmacist oversight regarding dispensing of medication, and the Five Rights administration safety check (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ), 2015b; U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2014). Furthermore, TJC encourages accredited hospitals to voluntarily report sentinel events related to medication

errors that reach patients. A sentinel event is defined as an error that has resulted in death, permanent harm, or severe temporary harm (The Joint Commission, 2017a).

In 2006, California Senate Bill 1301 required all healthcare facilities to report and investigate adverse events within 5 days of event discovery or within 24 hours depending on nature of the harm ("Alquist health facilities: reporting and inspection requirements, Senate Bill 1301," 2006). In the following year, the CDPH released the All Facilities Letter (AFL) 07-10 supporting the Senate bill asking hospitals to report adverse events to CDPH. The top priority for reporting adverse events is to include medication errors that cause patient death or disability (California Department of Public Health, 2007).

Internationally, medication errors are a persistent and recurrent problem (Keers, Williams, Cooke, & Ashcroft, 2013). From April 2015 to March 2016, 205,255 medication incidents reported in England and Wales equaled 11% of the reported total healthcare incidents (National Reporting and Learning System [NRLS], 2016). In 2012, in Ireland, 76,842 adverse clinical incidents were reported related to medication errors (Oglesby, 2012). A systematic review conducted in Middle Eastern countries reported prescription error rates as high as 90.5% and administration error rates between 9.4% to 80% (Alsulami, Conroy, & Choonara, 2013). Ashcroft and colleagues studied the medication prescription errors in 20 United Kingdom National Health Service hospitals over seven selected weekdays. They detected 11,235 prescribing errors, comprising 9% of total medication orders (Ashcroft et al., 2015).

At the national level, in its groundbreaking report "To Err is Human," the Institute of Medicine (IOM) estimated that patients are at risk for one medication error per hospital day and 98,000 deaths each year as result of errors (Institute of Medicine [IOM],

1999). James (2013) challenged the IOM estimate utilizing a new calculation tool. In the study, James estimated that there are 210,000 to 400,000 preventable adverse events that occur per year which contribute to the death of hospitalized patients (James, 2013). James further estimated that the number of preventable errors can be as high as 10 to 20 times higher than the death rate (James, 2013).

In 2013, the Partnership for Patients (PfP), a public-private partnership consisting of physicians, nurses, hospitals, employers, patients and their advocates, and the federal and state governments, began working together to improve the quality and safety of health care. The PfP is a safety initiative program from the Center for Medicare and Medicaid Services; its aim is to improve health care quality and safety for patients (Center for Medicare and Medicaid Services, n.d.). More than 4,000 hospitals across 16 Hospital Improvement Innovation Networks participate in the PfP. In 2011, the PfP set a goal to reduce patient harms in 11 core safety areas including preventable Adverse Drug Events (ADEs) among hospitalized patients by 40%. In 2012, PfP reported a 14% reduction in ADEs (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality [AHRQ], 2014b). From 2012 to 2013, an additional 3.8% decline in ADEs was reported (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality [AHRQ], 2014a). As a result of these reductions, approximately 50,000 fewer patients died in hospitals and approximately \$12 billion in health care costs were saved from 2010 to 2013 (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality [AHRQ], 2015a).

In recent years, TJC has documented the number of reported medication error-related sentinel events across the US. The TJC numbers only represent a portion of actual events that occur due to voluntary reporting. These fluctuated in recent years: 20 in 2014,

47 in 2015, and 33 in 2016. From 2005 to 2016, among sentinel events reported, 476 were medication errors, representing 4.78% of all sentinel events (The Joint Commission, 2017b). In 2015, the Federal Drug Administration (FDA) received 1.2 million adverse drug event reports, a 32% increase from the 875,186 adverse drug events reported in 2014 (Institute for Safe Medication Practices, 2016). While adverse drug events are not necessarily caused solely by medication errors, millions of adverse events reported to the FDA annually signify the numbers of patients impacted by errors.

From 2013 to 2015, 132 California hospitals voluntarily participated in the Patient Safety Organization (PSO) program which required that they report patient safety data. The PSO is a federally initiated patient safety program with aim to reduce patient harm and improve quality of patient care. During the two-year time frame, 920,000 medical errors were reported; 38% (350,355) of those were medication-related (Matheson, Keely, Gorman, & Brady, 2017). There are 533 licensed hospitals in California (Office of Statewide Health Planning and Development, 2017), which indicates only 24.7% (132/533) of the California hospitals participate in the PSO program. Actual numbers of medication errors could be higher if all hospitals participated in the PSO program.

The consequences of medication errors include longer hospital stays, patient mortality, and increased cost to the healthcare system (Nute, 2014). There may be at least 7,000 deaths each year in the US related to preventable medication errors (Institute of Medicine, 1999). In 2006, the IOM estimated that more than 1.5 million people were injured yearly by medication errors, leading to an estimated financial burden of \$3.5 billion (IOM, 2006). Based upon a review of four studies published between 2008 and 2011, all of which used the National Coordinating Council for Medication Errors

Reporting and Prevention scale and the Global Trigger tool for adverse events, James estimated two to four million serious patient adverse events occur annually due to medical errors (including medication errors) in hospitals with 210,000 of these were probably fatal (James, 2013).

Medication errors occur at higher rates than actually reported by hospital staff (Berdot et al., 2016; Vrbnjak, Denieffe, O'Gorman, & Pajnikihar, 2016). Lack of reporting is a concern because it is essential to have information about error-producing processes in order to reduce errors. Health care organizations need to be able to correct systematic errors. However, the errors must first be identified and reported. Investigation of errors, implementation of solutions, and learning from incidents can reduce future risks and promote the provision of high-quality patient care. Near misses are a special concern; these are errors that often go unreported because no patient harm occurs from an error. A near miss is a medication error that did not cause clinical harm due to early detection (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality, 2017b).

In hospital inpatient settings, nurses' roles in the medication administration process extend beyond simply preparing and administering medications as prescribed. Nurses are the last gate keepers before potential medication errors reach the patient. Nurses need to fully understand the process by which medication errors occur and the importance of reporting errors to proper administrative channels to allow improvements in patient care delivery systems. In the opinion of this author, no patient should experience error or be at risk for error when receiving health care. The goal for patient care is to be medication error free.

Problem Statement

In 2016, at a 102-bed community hospital in southern California, medications were administered 168,117 times. However, of these episodes of medication administration, only 27 medication errors were reported. When examining the medication errors, two did not meet the definition of medication error; these were not caused by direct medication administration to infants but rather exposure during the birthing process. Out of the remaining 25 cases, 20 were reported by pharmacists with only five reported by nurses. The five nurses who reported errors did so due to mandatory reporting when patients experienced problems or adverse reactions. Thus, no near miss incidents were reported in 2016, which, given the high number of medications administered at the hospital, supports underreporting is likely.

At this hospital, the medication management policy defined medication errors as “wrong drug, dosage, time, route or rate of administration, wrong patient, omission, duplication or administration without an order, and adverse reactions to medication (includes potential errors or ‘near misses’)” (Project Hospital, 2016). Conversations with nursing staff and pharmacists regarding medication error reporting determined that nurses and pharmacists did not consider near misses as medication errors and therefore, did not consider reporting them. This demonstrated that staff does not have a clear understanding of reportable medication errors and the criteria used for reporting, despite annual training on the topic. Reporting is especially important when medication errors do not cause patient harm since these experiences can be opportunities for performance improvement; staff can receive remediation education or systematic correction and processes of care can

be evaluated for potential change. These efforts should lead to improved reporting of medication errors and safer medication administration.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this project was to improve the project hospital's medication error reporting process in order to enhance reporting of all types of medication errors. This may improve medication safety and reduce medication errors. The following objectives guided the project:

- Refine the medication error reporting processes.
- Educate nurses and pharmacists regarding definitions of medication error, and reporting criteria.
- Develop strategies to address reporting accountability for medication errors.
- Evaluate nurse response to the changes and monitor medication errors reporting.

Supporting Framework

In this project, an adapted quality framework based on the Safety Action and Information Feedback from Incident Reporting (SAIFIR) framework was used. The SAIFIR framework was developed by Benn and colleagues (Benn et al., 2009) based on combination of systematic literature review and experts' interview feedbacks aim to improve utilization of error reporting system. Benn and colleagues developed the framework to improve incident reporting from organizational level, local level and regulatory level. The SAIFIR framework describes a systematic approach to identify contributing factors that cause failure in a practice (Benn et al., 2009; Parand et al., 2011). The systematic approach process was adapted in this project. The adapted SAIFIR

framework begins with organizational safety awareness with an emphasis on timely feedback to staff and ends with closing the loop of the safety feedback cycle (Figure 1).

The SAIFIR process starts with safety awareness. Awareness begins with front line staff recognizing that a reportable incident has occurred within the routine work environment. These incidents include medication errors that cause harm as well as near misses. At the project hospital, under-reporting of medication errors appeared to be related to lack of knowledge that an error has occurred. Staff may not have clear knowledge of error definition and expectations of reporting. Planned safety awareness reinforcement aimed to activate disclosure where staff report through proper channels or chain of command.

Benn et al. found a major barrier to reporting was feedback delays from managers to staff (Benn et al., 2009). In the safety feedback cycle, the first step is *timely response*. Timely response occurs when the manager or designee who receives the report acknowledges receipt of the delivered report. The next step is managerial advice to nursing staff involved and clarification if the content of the report is unclear. This *timely feedback* will give staff a sense of the recognition. This is in contrast to the perception of many staff that their incident reports fall into a “black hole” after the report is filed.

Following the timely response, an *analysis* regarding how the error occurred would be developed. This results in the formulation of a solution to prevent recurrence. At the project hospital, the unit director and Director of Pharmacy (DoP) investigate and gather the detailed information to determine root cause of errors. These investigations focus on systematic issues. The unit director and DoP design solutions to reduce recurrence of medication errors and create plans for implementation of solutions.

A barrier to staff reporting includes fear of punishment or being held solely responsible for the error. Therefore, at the close-of-the-loop process, there needs to be a focus on the processes to improve safety rather than a focus on placing individual blame. During this phase, corrective action is *communicate back to the staff* to promote transparency. The SAIFIR process reinforces the continuous cycle of work, where safety awareness is designed to trigger reporting, and safety feedback processes are designed to circulate information to frontline staff to promote voluntary reporting behavior (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Model for improvement: Adapted Safety Action and Information Feedback from Incident Report (SAIFIR). Adapted from "Feedback from incident reporting: information and action to improve patient safety," by Benn et al., 2009. *Quality Safety Health Care*, vol. 18(1), 11-21

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A search of literature for this project was performed using CINAHL and PubMed databases. Limitations for the search included English-language, full text and published articles between year 2007 to 2017. A foundational report “to error is human: building a safe health system” was used, and the report was published in 1999.

The search terms included nurse and hospital along with the terms medication error, prevent medication error, medication adverse event, medication error statistic, medication safety program, medication error reporting, voluntary reporting, and barriers to reporting, and near misses. A reference librarian specializing in nursing journals assisted to ensure a comprehensive search of existing articles. Reference lists of articles and studies identified were reviewed for additional studies to be included in the literature review.

The studies in the literature review took place in a variety of hospital unit settings (such as medical, surgical, pediatric, and general units/wards). Medication safety interventions focused on medication administration prevention strategies, and excluded computerized, physician-prescribed, and pharmacist-driven interventions. Rationale for the exclusion criteria is that the focus of this project is to improve medication safety both before and at the time of administration by bedside nurses.

Systematic reviews were included to evaluate the effectiveness of medication safety programs and barriers to voluntary reporting. Following a section on definition of terms, this literature review addresses two categories, barriers to voluntary medication error reporting (Table 1) and medication safety programs in hospitals (Table 2).

Definition of Terms and National Context

Medication error is a preventable event of inappropriate use of medication including errors of omission - that can lead to patient harm (National Coordinating Council of Medication Error Reporting and Prevention [NCCMERP], 2017). The NCCMERP is an independent group consisting of 27 national organizations. Its mission is to increase awareness and create strategies for decreasing medication errors through transparency and the sharing of preventative strategies (National Coordinating Council of Medication Error Reporting and Prevention, 2017). The NCCMERP categorized medication errors as the following (2001):

- Circumstances or events that have the capacity to cause error.
- An error occurred but the error did not reach the patient (An “error of omission” does reach the patient, also identified as a “near misses”).
- An error occurred that reached the patient but did not cause patient harm.
- An error occurred that resulted in the need for increased patient monitoring but no patient harm.
- An error occurred that resulted in the need for treatment or intervention and caused temporary patient harm.
- An error occurred that resulted in initial or prolonged hospitalization and caused temporary patient harm.
- An error occurred that resulted in permanent patient harm.
- An error occurred that resulted in a near-death event (e.g., anaphylaxis, cardiac arrest).

In 2002, TJC incorporated the Institute for Safety Medication Practice’s (ISMP) recommendation of error-prone medication abbreviations, symbols, and dose designation into the National Patient Safety Goals to mandate compliance by hospitals. The ISMP is the national nonprofit organization devoted entirely to medication error prevention and

safe medication use. The ISMP has been certified by the Agency for Healthcare Quality and Research (AHRQ) as a Patient Safety Organization (PSO) (Institute for Safe Medication Practices, 2017).

Barriers to Voluntary Medication Error Reporting

Medication errors can occur at any stage in the medication process. Actual administration by nurses of a drug is the last opportunity to stop a potential error before it reaches the patient. There are a number of reasons why medication errors are not reported as often as they occur. These include lack of awareness of error definitions (Berdot et al., 2016; Brady, Malone, & Fleming, 2009; Hartnell, MacKinnon, Sketris, & Fleming, 2012), clumsy or time-consuming reporting processes (Hartnell et al., 2012), and nurse perception of fear and blame or retribution (Bayazidi, Zarezadeh, Zamanzadeh, & Parvan, 2012; Benn et al., 2009; Vrbnjak et al., 2016).

While studies show that medication errors can be reduced with the use of technologies such as computerized prescriptions, automatic dispensing, and barcoded scanners (Radley et al., 2013; U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2014), errors and near misses can still occur at the time of medication administration since computerized technology does not eliminate human error. For example, a medical record system does not capture all patient information related to allergies or disease processes unless this is manually inputted. Nurses administering medications may be unaware of gaps of information in the medical record which can potentially harm patients.

Once a medication error occurs, it is the ethical responsibility of the nurse to report it (Kavanagh, 2017). Medication error reporting requires that nurses have knowledge and understanding of hospital medication safety policy (Adhikari, Tocher,

Smith, Corcoran, & MacArthur, 2014; Bayazidi et al., 2012; Keers et al., 2013). Policies with standardized definitions provide nurses with guidelines as to what and how to report (Hartnell et al., 2012). This is crucial in reporting practices, where nurses can recognize an error or near miss and activate the reporting process (Berdot et al., 2016; Brady et al., 2009).

Studies where nurses' perspectives on medication error reporting were addressed showed that a medication error is less likely to be reported if it caused no harm to the patient (Farag, Blegen, Gedney-Lose, Lose, & Perkhounkova, 2017; Harkanen, Saano, & Vehvilainen-Julkunen, 2017; Parand et al., 2011; Yung, Yu, Chu, Hou, & Tang, 2016). In other words, medication errors tend to be reported when the outcome causes patient harm. However, based upon the NCCMERP categories, patient harm is not the only criteria for reporting. Voluntary reporting of medication errors occurs especially when there is no patient harm (Bayazidi et al., 2012; Farag et al., 2017). Reasons for this include the belief that medication errors are not worthy of reporting when a patient is not harmed (Farag et al., 2017). Or lack of understanding of the benefits that can be learned from near misses (Yung et al., 2016). Knowledge of near miss errors can allow personnel to improve the system for medication safety, and thus, prevent future mistakes.

Other barriers to nurse reporting are nurses' perceptions of fear and blame. A systematic review of 38 studies found that several types of fear and blame perceptions prevented nurse medication error reporting. These include individual blame, fear of disciplinary action from managers, consequence of error, and fear of lawsuits from patients (Vrbnjak et al., 2016). The culture of the work place (e.g., hospital unit) also plays a key role in medication error reporting as nurses are less likely to report when they

do not see the benefit of reporting, as well as when they do not receive a consequence for not reporting (Bayazidi et al., 2012; Hartnell et al., 2012; Vrbnjak et al., 2016).

Strategies for reporting medication errors involve staff nurses, managers, and risk managers. However, incident reporting systems often involve a one-way flow of information. That is, managers or designees receive the medication error report, and information about how the error was handled does not flow back to reporting nurses (Aydon, Hauck, Zimmer, & Murdoch, 2016; Benn et al., 2009). These nurses are left with no feedback on what caused the error, whether it was a systemic issue, or how to improve practices to prevent future errors.

Medication Safety Programs in Hospitals

The following section provides an evaluation of medication programs designed to improve medication safety in hospitals which focus on interventions that enhance staff knowledge in medication error definition, improve ease of reporting system, and improve feedback sharing process to the frontline staff.

In order to improve voluntary reporting, frontline staff need an understanding of reportable incident criteria. When reportable incident criteria are standardized and well-defined throughout the organization, potential confusion related to reportable events is minimized. Standardization of medication error definition is essential to enhance nursing knowledge and when missing, is a barrier to reporting (Hartnell et al., 2012). When interviewed, frontline staff (pharmacist, physicians, and nurses) expressed the importance of a standardized reporting guideline as a facilitator to medication error reporting (Hartnell et al., 2012). Several programs have attempted to address the standardization of safe medication practices and reporting. In a systematic review, Keers, Williams, Cooke,

Walsh and Ashcroft (2014) concluded that successful interventions to reduce medication error in hospitals include staff training and education in medicine use, bar code technology, interventions designed to minimize interruption, and double check processes (Keers, Williams, Cooke, Walsh, & Ashcroft, 2014). In a systematic review and meta-analysis of seven studies, increased staff knowledge about safe medication practice was observed to reduce medication error occurrence (Berdot et al., 2016).

In addition to training, using direct observation and audits of medication administration can strengthen safe medication administration practice. In a Chinese hospital that included direct observation of medication administration, Xu, Li, Ye, and Lu (2014) showed an 11% increase in compliance with medication administration policy and procedure following implementation of a multi-pronged medication safety program (Xu, Li, Ye, & Lu, 2014). In their program, audit and direct observations with immediate feedback reinforced the importance of adherence to standard medication administration and enhanced compliance of medication error reporting. Although the study was conducted in a foreign country, the implementation of direct observations and audits are common healthcare practices in the US.

Incident reporting programs using either paper or computer input provide staff with portals for reporting errors. When a reporting portal is deemed user friendly and less time consuming, reporting rates increase (Bayazidi et al., 2012; Hartnell et al., 2012). A study using both focus groups and surveys of frontline staff (pharmacist, nurses, physician) found that the time spent on reporting was considered a burden; staff stated that if the system used to report was easier to use, they would report more frequently (Hartnell et al., 2012).

A case study demonstrated that differences in implementation of a reporting system led to differences in staff perception of reportable events, reporting practices, and unit safety culture (Hewitt, Chreim, & Forster, 2016). Researchers compared the similarities and differences of the reporting process in two units using the same incident reporting system. Unit A had a reporting practice that was outcome-driven when patient harm occurred. In this unit, the incident analysis focused on individual problems with feedback aimed at the individual level. The staff in this unit was educated on logistics of reporting not the rationale of reporting, and the staff or the leader of the unit did not participate in designing the reporting. In comparison, the Unit B staff was educated on logistics and the rationale for reporting. The feedback related to medication errors was shared with the team using various methods including meetings, a newsletter, and participation in question and answer sessions. The focus of analysis was a systems approach instead of individual blame. As a result, Unit B staff reported not only errors that caused patient harm, but also near miss incidents (Hewitt et al., 2016).

Several factors have been found to support nurse error reporting including closed form incident reporting. In a systematic review of 29 studies of incident reporting systems all over the world, Benn and colleagues found that closed form incident reporting among staff encouraged reporting (Benn et al., 2009). Closed form incident reporting involves resolution of the incident with feedback given to reporting staff; thus, managers or designees share information related to medication errors, which can increase staff knowledge and confidence in reporting (Benn et al., 2009). When staff received feedback about medication errors and learned how and why errors occurred, medication error events decreased (McClead et al., 2014).

Another factor affecting success of a medication safety program was having a supportive unit culture which promotes voluntary reporting (Hewitt et al., 2016; Smith & Haig, 2005). A supportive culture entails the leader's emphasis on safety as an organizational priority and reinforcement of expectations to report all medication errors and near misses. In addition, a non-punitive environment exists where no individual blame occurs with error discovery (Adhikari et al., 2014; Bayazidi et al., 2012; Hewitt et al., 2016). Frontline staff reported that one of the facilitators to medication error reporting was to receive feedback from managers (Hartnell et al., 2012).

Summary

The literature review supported three common interventions in hospitals that may improve medication safety. The first is education and training about standardized medication error reporting protocols. The second is improved logistics of reporting systems to reduce staff burden of reporting. Last is improved feedback to frontline staff, including sharing changes made to resolve errors. A non-punitive environment can be achieved when staff understands that medication error reporting promotes patient safety and should not end up in individual blame. In return, the culture will constantly support staff to identify errors to improve safety medication administration. Therefore, the goal of this project is to implement these interventions to improve medication safety in the project hospital.

METHODS

Medication errors can occur at any stage of the medication management process (e.g., ordering, transcription, dispensing, preparation, administration). Considered preventable, medication errors can cause patient harm. Reporting errors is part of the process of error reduction. Medication errors are under-reported due to knowledge gaps in definition, tediousness of the reporting process, as well as the time it takes away from patient care. Lack of timely feedback to staff also hinders their willingness to report. The initial focus of this project was to amend the project hospital's medication error reporting policy, specifically, to have it be congruent with the NCCMERP medication error definition. After consulting the literature, the project was expanded to address staff reporting accountability including nurse education and a timely feedback cycle.

Setting

This doctoral project aimed to improve medication safety at a 102-bed community hospital in the California Inland Empire. The project was implemented on the 62-bed Medical Surgical and Telemetry (MST) unit where 50% of the nursing staff (40 nurses) had less than three years of acute hospital experience. Before the project, medication error reporting processes involved staff voluntarily self-reporting error and pharmacy department retrospective chart review. The project hospital uses software (Verge Solution©) for all safety-related reporting (Verge Solution, n.d.). When safety incidents are reported, the system auto-populates a notification that is sent to the director of the unit or designee. The unit director receives a notification when a medication error is filed directly by staff. Any medication-related incidents discovered retrospectively by the pharmacy department are filed directly by the DoP. The DoP forwards incidents to the

respective unit director, who investigates and/or follows up with nurses. Medication error data is aggregated by the DoP and reported to the Medication Safety and Pharmacy, Therapeutic, Nutrition and Infection Control (PTNIC) Committees. Members of these committees make recommendations to improve medication safety in the hospital. The PTNIC meeting minutes are shared with the Governing Board.

Ethical Considerations

This quality improvement project aimed to improve medication safety processes in a community hospital. Data used was de-identified and aggregated from reports; no individual patient or individual front line staff data was reported. Therefore, no institutional review board approval was sought. Permission to implement the project was granted by the Chief Nursing Office (Appendix A).

Needs Assessment

In the project hospital's 2016 medication safety report, the number of medication error reports ($n = 25$) was relatively small in proportion to the total amount/number of medication administrations performed in 2016 ($n = 168,117$). A very small percentage of front line staff voluntarily reported medication errors (5 out of the 25 events were reported by nurses). The project hospital's policies "Medication Management Program," "Adverse Event Reporting," and "Medication Errors" were reviewed; gaps were identified in the area of medication error definition and the reporting process in all three policies.

Since 2006, the project hospital has taken part in the annual Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ) of Patient Safety Culture Survey. AHRQ is the health services research arm of the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, and

is considered the lead federal agency for research on health care quality, costs, outcomes, and patient safety (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality, 2017a). The Patient Safety Culture Survey is conducted annually along with a skills fair, which is mandatory for all staff to attend. The survey consists of questions that address patient safety from multiple areas: (a) teamwork within units, (b) supervisor/manager expectations and actions promoting patient safety, (c) organizational learning-continuous improvement, (d) management support for patient safety, (e) overall perceptions of patient safety, (f) feedback and communication about error, (g) communication openness, (h) frequency of events reported, (i) teamwork across units, (j) staffing, (k) handoffs and transitions, (l) nonpunitive response to errors. Given 2016 and 2017 data on the Patient Safety Culture Survey, items specific to medication error reporting that are relevant to this project are below (Figure 2):

- In September 2016, in the category of communication openness, for the question regarding “feedback and communication error,” only 34% of 317 staff members polled stated that they “always” receive feedback about changes put into place based on event reports. In August 2017, only 31% of 317 staff members stated “always.”
- Furthermore, in 2016, 44% answered “always” to the question “we are informed about errors happen in this unit” while 41% of 319 staff answered “always” to the same question in 2017.

The AHRQ results demonstrated a need to improve communication and timely feedback to frontline staff regarding errors and changes that need to take place to correct the errors.

Figure 2. Percentage of staff who responded “always” to AHRQ Patient Safety Culture survey questions. Q1: we are given feedback about changes put into place based on event reports. Q2: we are informed about errors that happen in this unit.

Analysis of the process gaps and the aim of this doctoral project were discussed with the Chief Nursing Officer (CNO) and the DoP. The CNO granted permission for the project to be implemented in August 2017. The DoP also agreed to participate.

Experiences with the Current Reporting System

During spring 2016, the project lead (who is also the MST director) assisted a MST staff nurse to report one medication error using the Verge Solution Reporting Incident Report (RIR) website (Verge Solution, n.d.). The RIR reporting tool was handed down through the project hospital’s Corporation contract; it is a “one size fits all” reporting system. Thus, employees and local leaders were not involved in designing or adopting the system. The reporting system was supposed to synchronize the electronic medical record with current inpatient data; however, staff reports that this is not the case. For example, the system does not contain all inpatient admission information and physician lists are not updated automatically.

In this experience with the RIR, the reporting tool was not user friendly and time consuming, taking approximately 20 minutes to complete. The system required completion of three pages of information for the medication error report. However, in actuality, the reporting nurse was only required to complete key pieces of information on the first page. The report can actually be submitted after the first page is completed, which the nurses may not be aware of (as with the case above); no cue is given to the reporting nurses that this is the case.

Following this experience, informal interviews were conducted with 10 MST nurses with various years of experience. All nurses expressed similar concerns regarding the reporting process and the excessive length of time it takes to complete. Nurses reported spending additional unnecessary time trying to find information on multiple pages, which is irrelevant to their role. This showed a potential for process improvement related to staff nurses reporting medication errors.

Procedures

As described in the SAIFIR framework, the medication safety process starts with staff awareness that an error has occurred, which should trigger reporting. In order to recognize that an error has occurred, staff nurses need to have knowledge about medication errors, and when to initiate reporting. The hospital policies were revised to include the definition of medication error, to refine the medication error reporting process, and to clarify accountability of reporting. Unit staff was educated about policy revisions in February 2018.

Revisions to the Medication Error policy included two changes. First, the definition of medication error was changed to the NCCMERP medication error

definition; this definition, which includes *near miss* errors that are caught before reaching the patient, was incorporated into all hospital medication safety policies. Second, because a key element of voluntary reporting is that staff feel safe to report their mistake and not be afraid of performance improvement punishment from managers, revised policies stress the non-punitive nature of reporting.

The revised policy (“Medication Errors”) went through the hospital approval process in the following order: Professional Practice Committee (September 2017), Clinical Leadership Committee (September 2017), Medication Safety Committee (October 2017), PTNIC (November 2017), and Governing Board (November 2017). The policies “Medication Management Program” and “Adverse Event Reporting” were reviewed with no change. No other policies were impacted by the revision of “Medication Error” policy.

Staff education was implemented after the policy was approved. Part of the project involved developing and implementing an educational intervention for staff on the MST unit. The project lead began education regarding all medication policies (“Medication Management Program,” “Adverse Event Reporting,” and “Medication Errors”) on February 8, 2018 through a mandatory staff meeting. Following this, content about medication safety policies will be included in the MST shift huddle for four weeks. The four-week cycle was selected to ensure that all staff receives the education as some staff may be on leave. Charge nurses and lead pharmacists will also undergo education in the spring of 2018 as they will serve as resources for staff nurses.

Medication safety education was also introduced during hospital orientation (second Tuesday and Wednesday of the month; the first orientation occurred on January

8th and 9th, 2018 with two topics: brief introduction of medication error definition and reporting accountability. The orientation emphasized the rationale for reporting and sharing knowledge regarding the “whys” behind reporting. In the future, this content will be incorporated into MST new hire orientation packets. New hire education for 2018 will start in March. The project lead will coordinate with the hospital educator and the DoP to create different scenarios of medication errors and near misses to enhance new hires’ knowledge. A post-test questionnaire will be developed to test understanding.

The project hospital’s reporting system involves a system that has been contracted, and therefore cannot be altered, so education to the staff addressed this system. Literature review evidence indicated that staff are less likely to report if the process is too time consuming. In order to simplify the reporting process, a reporting reference guide (Appendix B) was developed and shared with MST staff during the staff meeting. The reference guide focused on the key questions that should be completed by nurses and contained instructions of appropriate information required for the questions. This eliminates the need for nurses to go beyond the information reportable by nurses and should eliminate time for reporting. The reference guide was laminated and inserted into the unit resource binder. Charge nurses were trained to be the super users as well as resource persons who will assist nurses in completing reports.

The safety feedback cycle consists of three steps. The first step is a timely response, where the manager or designee acknowledges receipt of a medication error report, provides advice, and seeks clarification about the incident. Currently, Verge Solution does not have the functionality to allow managers/directors to send an acknowledgement notification to the person making the report. Given this situation, the

project lead (MST director), CNO, and DoP created a generic acknowledgment message to be sent to the reporter's work email (if the reporter did not opt to report anonymously). In the second step of the cycle, the MST director together with the DoP will investigate and analyze the root cause of the incident. They will determine whether the error was an individual personnel mistake or a systems concern. The focus of this step is to avoid individual blame. However, the individual will be held accountable based on the incident or when there is a trend of repetitive problematic behaviors.

The last step of the safety feedback cycle is to close the loop to inform frontline staff of changes made to address medication error incidents. The plan going forward is that information will be shared daily at the beginning of the shift huddle under the clinical update section for two weeks after any medication error incident. The information will cover two main points: "what happened" and "what did we learn from it." Any staff information will be de-identified.

The last step to improve medication safety is to implement a medication administration audit through direct observation. The project hospital started the medication administration audit process in February 2018 after the MST staff education and meeting. Audits will be completed by shift charge nurses or resource nurses. Observation audits will be viewed as teaching opportunities for staff. If near misses are observed, charge or resource nurses will discuss what happened and provide timely feedback to frontline nurses post medication administration. Another purpose of this unit-based audit is to reinforce frontline staff's safety medicine administration practice. Audits will be submitted to the unit director to aggregate for evaluation.

Plan for Evaluation

The evaluation of this project's completeness includes:

- Approval of revised medication safety policies (e.g., approval by the Governing Board by November 2017);
- Development of educational 4-phase intervention with reporting reference guide;
- Training on MST unit that began February 2018; post-training discussions shows that staff are knowledgeable about medication error reporting processes;
- Monitor number of near misses reported in the second quarter 2018 (April through June) in the DoP's medication safety report;
- Monitor total errors relative to total opportunities of error from the medication administration audits on MST unit; compare these quarterly;
- Informally collect staff feedback regarding the new medication error reporting process beginning February 2018, with findings logged in a journal;
- Monitor AHRQ Culture of Patient Safety Survey questions (a) we are given feedback about changes put into place based on event reports and (b) we are informed about errors that happen in this unit.

ACCOMPLISHMENTS

The policy review and revision was completed in September 2017. The NCCMERP's medication error definition was added to the Medication Error policy. The policy also states that all staff are responsible for medication error reporting and reporting should be done through Verge Solution. The Medication Error policy stated "in depth analysis is done primarily on system and process, not individual performance..." to support and develop a blame-free culture when errors occur. The policy was approved in the PTNIC on October 24, 2017 and was approved by the MEC and the Governing Board joint committee on November 3, 2017. The two related policies "Medication Management Program" and "Adverse Event Reporting" were reviewed with no changes made.

The CNO, Human Resource Supervisor, DoP, Nurse Directors, Performance Improvement department representative, nurse educator and other multi-disciplinary team members met on December 15, 2017 to review and revise the new hire orientation agenda for 2018. The agenda covered the content that states no individual blame for voluntary error reporting, unless the error was caused by reckless behavior. The pharmacist section included the "near miss reporting" and "medication error." This new hire orientation agenda was implemented in January 2018.

The Verge Solution incident reporting software reference guide was developed to assist staff to avoid unnecessary steps for filing an incident report. Using this guide should reduce the time spent reporting a medication error by highlighting key questions that staff are required to complete. The reference guide was laminated and inserted into

the pilot unit resource binder in February 2018. The reference guide was introduced to staff at the February 8 staff meeting.

The project lead met with the charge nurses in December 2017 and January 2018 to gather input on the current medication passing audit tool. Questions discussed included whether it comprehensively addressed medication safety at each stage involved in the medication administration process. The project lead and DoP revised the tool to incorporate recommendations from charge nurses. The new audit tool included audit questions that addressed each stage of medication administration, from prescribing, to transcribing, dispensing, administering, and monitoring (Appendix B). The consensus was that any “no” to a question will be considered a near miss; and will require an incident report. The DoP and project lead will review incidents reported and categorize incidents to determine root cause. Categories include omission error, incorrect time, wrong drug, incorrect administration technique. The MST unit charge nurses and lead pharmacist attended the education session on February 1, 2018 to learn about use of the audit tool and changes in the “Medication Error” policy. This educational session focused on the need for consistency and a non-biased audit process. In addition, charge nurses were instructed on the incident reporting reference guide.

Education on medication error policy and medication error reporting processes began at the mandatory MST staff meeting on February 8, 2018. Staff who attended reviewed and signed the acknowledgement of receipt of the “Medication Error” policy at this time. The DoP attended the meeting and covered content about the medication error reporting update. One aim of the material presented at this time was to create and support a blame-free environment, hopefully allowing for the open discussion of errors and the

impact of errors to the hospital. The DoP informed staff of the pharmacy department's process for identifying medication errors. The staff were informed about reasons for the medication audit process. Twenty-seven staff attended the meeting and shared incidents they had encountered such as medication not available due to no supply; slow pharmacist turnaround time for medication verification; conflicting instruction between physician and pharmacist, and documentation of administration. Content about medication error reporting will also be included in weekly shift huddles by MST charge nurses for four weeks in order to reach all staff. Similar content was covered as part of DoP's new hire orientation section in January. Future new hires will be educated on the methods of error reporting and the ethical responsibilities for reporting regardless patient was harmed or not; the no blame culture will be stressed.

The generic email acknowledgment to staff that will be sent once an incident report is received was approved by the CNO in January 2018. Now, any staff member who does not file an incident report anonymously will receive an email response from the unit director stating "The incident report you filed has been received and is currently under review and investigation. Thank you for your support in making our facility a safer place for patients and staff."

Next Steps

This quality improvement project is ongoing and currently no results are available. This project requires continuous monitoring using the metrics in the evaluation plan, with revisions of the process as needed. The project lead will informally collect staff feedback regarding the medication error reporting process. All feedback gathered will be reviewed with DoP to evaluate areas of improvement. The DoP will begin

including near misses in medication safety reports. The project lead and DoP will meet bi-weekly and as needed to review medication error reports. The findings and interventions implemented will be presented to staff during shift huddles.

If the project is moving in the desired direction, voluntary near misses reporting should increase as staff gain knowledge and understand the responsibility of reporting. Quarter 1 and 2 medication safety reports will be compared to determine if there is an increase in voluntary reporting. The project lead will analyze the AHRQ Patient Safety Culture survey results collected during the August 2018 skills fair. The 2018 results will be compared to those from 2016 and 2017 to identify changes in staff perception of medication safety; specifically, whether they perceived receipt of feedback about changes put into place based on event reports and being informed about errors that happen on their unit.

DISCUSSION

Safe medication administration requires a multifaceted approach that includes staff competency, standardized policies, and a supportive culture with timely feedback to staff. A systematic approach that minimizes individual blame and assures timely feedback to staff is crucial in promoting voluntary error reporting. This project adapted the SAIFIR framework to promote medication safety on the 62-bed MST unit. Steps taken should enhance the likelihood of staff reporting even when errors cause no harm. The revised “Medication Error” policy standardized the medication error definition and now includes near misses that cause no patient harm as medication errors.

During a TJC survey of the project hospital in fall 2017, surveyors launched a focused inquiry about actions that this hospital was using to prevent errors and strategies to mitigate near misses. While the project hospital’s leadership had been interested in the doctoral project prior to the survey, they became notably more supportive when the project lead was able to discuss specific steps being taken as a result of this project with surveyors. As a result, the CNO asked educators to add content about Just Culture and nurse accountability for error reporting to the new hire orientation. This demonstrated that hospital leaders were determined to improve patient safety.

Throughout the project, multiple people have supported the project. Working directly with the project lead, the DoP has been extremely supportive about the process changes. Other department directors have been excited to have changes rolled out in their departments.

The majority of staff in the project unit (MST) are newly graduated nurses with less than three years of experience. This was both an advantage and disadvantage when

implementing changes. During the education session with charge nurses and the pharmacist lead, charge nurses expressed concerns regarding some staff medication administration practices that were considered convenient but had a potential risk for error. Charge nurses were concerned that new nurses would have a difficult time adjusting to new practices that are different from what they were taught previously. In reality, these new nurses were often receptive to changes and adapted easily to recommended changes. For example, nurses seemed open to changes in the medication error reporting process, especially when the reference guide was shown to them and an explanation was given about the limits to required questions for nurses. However, the role of being a patient advocate (in terms of safety) was sometimes a secondary priority due to the many challenges new nurses face with having to adjust to their new role.

The importance of a supportive culture and staff accountability is critical in achieving patient safety in this community hospital. The SAIFIR model was explained to charge nurses; notably, if new hires do not understand correction medication safety practices, they will not be able to follow the hospital's standard of practice. The project lead also discussed with charge nurses that the culture of patient safety needs to be supported in order to be changed and sustained and this can begin immediately with all staff. Charge nurses came to the agreement that everyone should be held to the same standard when it comes to the patient safety. Charge nurses were educated on the audit process with an emphasis on accountable results that should enhance nurse medication administration processes. Charge nurses provided positive feedback on the SAIFIR framework in the feedback cycle; they stated that knowing which type of medication

errors happen in the unit will increase staff awareness and recognition of error occurrence.

As MST director, the project lead found that giving timely feedback can be time consuming and difficult, just as nurses experienced reporting medication errors. However, feedback is as imperative as nurses' self-reporting to the cycle of medication safety. Breaking any part of the chain will break the pathway to becoming a zero-harm patient organization. The project lead was shocked by comments and incidents staff shared at the February meeting about issues related to patient safety (especially from night shift staff). She had assumed that by instructing and disseminating protocols in the unit over the past months, staff were sufficiently prepared to competently replicate the revised process. However, staff reported a knowledge gap related to reportable events. Like the literature review indicated (Farag et al., 2017; Harkanen et al., 2017; Parand et al., 2011), staff still did not consider bringing an error to the attention of superiors or reporting when they perceived there was no harm to patients. At the staff meeting, actual encounters were discussed; this helped expose elements of incidents that made them worth reporting. As part of the future plan, the project lead will continue to invite staff to share their personal experience at meetings to increase awareness.

Ensuring a culture of safety is a complex process and is not likely to change overnight. In fact, it requires dedication and commitment from staff at all levels to fully use their knowledge, expertise and roles to prevent patient harm. This project hospital aims to achieve a zero-harm patient safety culture, which takes more than just having a vision at the leadership level. Since front line staff perceptions of safety practice may differ from their leaders, strategies to gather and provide timely feedback to staff is

essential to ensure a common understanding is consistent in the organization. This medication safety project is a small part of the hospital's overall culture of safety. The project lead hopes to promote the no blame and non-punitive culture in the MST unit as a starting point that will encourage staff to voluntarily report patient safety concerns in other units. Beginning with the MST unit, the medication safety project results will be shared and as appropriate, moved throughout other departments in the hospital.

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APPENDIX A
PROJECT HOSPITAL'S APPROVAL EMAIL

The screenshot shows an email client window with the following details:

- Subject:** RE: Project to Improve Medication Safety in MST Unit - Message (HTML)
- Sender:** Gail Aviado (MHMC)
- Recipient:** Jessica Lee (MHMC)
- Date:** Wed 3/14/2018 9:26 AM
- Body:**

Jessica,

The hospital supports this project. This will be part of our initiative in promoting just culture. Let me know if you need assistance from leadership. Good luck!

Kindly,

Gail Aviado, MSN, RN | Administrator/Chief Nursing Officer/Risk Manager
5000 San Bernardino St | Montclair, CA 91763 | T 909.625.8192 | F 909.626.4777
gaviado@primehealthcare.com
- Footer:**

15 TOP HEALTH SYSTEM **100 TOP HOSPITALS**

Notice: This e-mail (including attachments) is covered by the Electronic Communications Privacy Act, 18 U.S.C. 2510-2521, is confidential and may be legally privileged. If you are not the intended recipient, you are hereby notified that any retention, dissemination, distribution, or copying of this communications is strictly prohibited. Please reply to the sender that you have received the message in error, then delete it. Thank you.

APPENDIX B

RIR MEDICATION ERROR REPORTING REFERENCE GUIDE

Medication and other substance RIR Reference Guide

1. Open Intranet page using Internet Explorer from any computer in the unit
2. Look for **Risk Identification Report** on the right side on Intranet Page

3. Select **“Medication and Other Substance”**

4. Complete highlighted questions

Patient Safety Event Report

Date/Time of Event

* Date and time when event occurred

*

Reporter's Name

* Your name or you can file anonymously

Prefer to remain anonymous

Location of Event

Organization:
Location:
[Select Location](#) | [Reset](#)

Click "Select Location" and pick MST from the drop down menu

Was a secondary location involved in the event?

Yes No

Who reported the event or unsafe condition?

Healthcare professional Select appropriate personnel that first discovered the event

Healthcare worker, including nursing assistant, patient transport/retrieval personnel, assistant/orderly, clerical/administrative personnel, interpreter/translator, technical/laboratory personnel, pastoral care personnel, biomedical engineer, housekeeping, maintenance, patient care assistant, or administrator/manager

Emergency service personnel, including police officer, fire fighter, or other emergency service officer

Patient, family member, volunteer, caregiver, or home assistant

Unknown

Other

Who was the patient involved?

Select Patient | Reset

Patient Not Found

No Patient Involved

Patient Information Unknown

Pick "Patient Information Unknown" here. Enter pt's H# in next question

***Describe the event exactly as it occurred (please indicate specific body parts/site affected if applicable)**

1. Enter pt's H# and pt's name here.

2. Detailed description of the event.

Was the patient harmed?

Yes No

If unknown, pick "No"

How was this event discovered? (Check all that apply)

Assessment after event

Report by family or visitors

Report by patient

Report by resident, fellow, or student

Report by staff member

Review of record or chart

Witnessed/Involved

Select most appropriate description about the event

What type of patient safety event is being reported?

Incident (Reached the patient)

Near Miss (Did not reach the patient)

Unsafe Condition

Select most appropriate description about the event

State Mandated Reportable Event?

Yes No

Pick "No" (Risk manager will determine if event is reportable)

Was your supervisor notified?

Yes No

Where did the event occur, or, if an unsafe condition, where does it exist?

Inpatient general care area (e.g., medical/surgical unit)

Special care area (e.g., ICU, CCU, NICU)

Labor and delivery

Operating room or procedure area (e.g., cardiac catheter lab, endoscopy area), including PACU or recovery area

Radiology/imaging department, including onsite mobile units

Pharmacy

Other

Laboratory, including pathology department and blood bank

Emergency department

Other area within the facility

Outpatient care area

Outside area (i.e., grounds of this facility)

Unknown

Select most appropriate description about how the event was discovered

Further explanation of discovery

May skip if no further explanation

***Type of Event**

Medication and Other Substance

***Injury or Outcome: (Check all that apply)**

<input type="checkbox"/> None noted	<input type="checkbox"/> Death	<input type="checkbox"/> Neurological impairment/deficit
<input type="checkbox"/> Arrest with code	<input type="checkbox"/> Delay in Services	<input type="checkbox"/> Patient/family Dissatisfaction
<input type="checkbox"/> Aspiration/asphyxia	<input type="checkbox"/> Fracture	<input type="checkbox"/> Respiratory impairment
<input type="checkbox"/> Bruise/abrasion	<input type="checkbox"/> Laceration	<input type="checkbox"/> Sprain, strain
<input type="checkbox"/> Burn	<input type="checkbox"/> Laceration requiring suture	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown at report time

Check all that apply. If no injury noted at time of reporting, pick "none noted"

Physician involved in addressing immediate needs resulting from the event?

Yes No NA

ALWAYS notify physician when a medication error occurred and reached patient. Pick "No" for near misses (error did not reach patient)

Additional monitoring, treatment or interventions have been taken as a result of this event?

What actions/interventions were taken as a result of this event?

Has the event been discussed with the patient or any family member?

Yes No Unknown

- When error is reported to physician, let physician talk to pt/family member. Select "Unknown" if you do not know if physician talked to the pt yet.
- Select "unknown" If reporting near misses.

Next page >> [Event Details](#)

What incorrect action was taken? Choose the most relevant:

Other: (Please specify)

At what stage in the process did the event originate, regardless of the stage at which it was discovered?

Other: (Please specify)

Click "Save form" when all the required information is entered

Last step

When an ID# displayed, that means the incident is successfully filed. Click "continue" and close the window.

Medication and Other Substance

 Unique Id: EVD0081395
Continue

APPENDIX C

Medication Administration Observation Audit

Name of Nurse: _____

Date: _____

Name of Evaluator: _____

Directions:

1. **DO NOT** notify the individual being observed ahead of time
2. Observe the process utilized for administering medication from start to finish
3. At the end of medication pass process, provide individual with immediate feedback regarding any steps missed or done incorrectly
4. Return audit guide to your immediate supervisor

#	Criteria for Med Administration & Documentation	Yes	No	Comments
1	Hand Hygiene prior to medication administration			
2	Prepares meds for one patient only			
3	All meds available in the unit			
4	Verification of meds labeled throughout entire process (IV syringe labeled, crushing device/bag labeled)			
5	Verifies allergies			
6	Performs the 8 rights			
	Right patient (use of 2 identifiers)			
	Right Medication			
	Right Dose			
	Right Route			
	Right Time			
	Right Documentation: see #14 below			
	Right reason			
	Right response			
7	Medication corresponds to eMAR			
8	Each individual medication opened at bedside			
9	Nurse inspects medication and checks for expiration date			
10	Nurse explains med being administered, including side effects			
11	Nurse maintains focus during medication administration			
12	IV port is swabbed before accessing IV			
13	No meds transported in nurse's pockets			
14	Documentation in eMAR occurs AFTER meds given			
15	Potential safety concerns noted (distractions/interruptions)			
16	Incorrect medications set aside and reported to pharmacy			
17	Medication Error (including near misses) If yes, proceed to #18 below			
18	Medication error documented on incident report			

Evaluator notes/comment box

APPENDIX D

TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Table 1

Barriers to Voluntary Medication Error Reporting

Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample & setting	Measurements/operational	Findings	Conclusions & Notes
To explore nurses Medication Error (ME) reporting and near miss barriers from individual level to organizational barriers (Vrbnjak et al., 2016)	Systematic review Mix of qualitative and quantitative studies	English language, between 01/1981 to 04/2015. 4038 records found, 38 included.	One of authors assessed eligibility and relevance of all titles and abstracts search result. Two authors independently decided on final inclusion. Decision was validated by third author. Three authors independently assessed quality of studies using MMAT criteria.	Culture barrier: safety culture promoted reporting. Reporting varies among units due to diff. unit culture; medical surgical ward reported to have lower reporting rate. Reporting system: lack of clear definition & standard of ME reduced the reporting, if the tool used to report is time consuming & viewed as a burden to report. Nurse less likely to report. Management behavior barrier: managers who focus on finding the offender rather than process. Lack of	Unit culture can be stronger than organization culture. Managers' reinforcement of reporting, timely feedback, reward of good performance and implementation of quality initiative helped staff to report. Notes: Staff clear understanding of error and managers reinforce expectation help to build a unit culture to promote voluntary reporting. Review and/or revise the ME reporting policy, to include clear definition of ME.

Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample & setting	Measurements/operational	Findings	Conclusions & Notes
				<p>feedback also impeded reporting. Front line staff less likely to report if they don't see the benefit of reporting.</p> <p>Personal & professional barrier: nurses fear the mistake would be held against them. Fear of punishment. Fear that they might be viewed as incompetent by peers.</p> <p>Accountability barrier: inadequate understanding of what constituted error ↓ Reporting. Nurses do not want to "tell" on their colleague.</p>	
To examine relationship among work environment (manger leadership style and safety climate), social capital (warmth, belonging relationship and organization trust) and nurses'	Cross-sectional descriptive Questionnaire Convenience sample	5 hospitals (3 community, 2 critical care access hospital) affiliated with Midwestern health care system Inclusion: Full time & part time nurses.	Study introduced to (ED) nurse at monthly meeting; Package was sent out to nurses' work mailbox Weekly reminder \$10 compensation check when completed survey is mail in.	RN exp. average 8.3 yrs (range 1-38 yrs) 55% Associate degree/diploma 45% BSN + 71.8% stated very likely to report if	Nurse manager's leadership style (transactional) was weakly associated with willingness to report. Timely feedback had positive impact on nurses' voluntary ME reporting.

Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample & setting	Measurements/operational	Findings	Conclusions & Notes
willingness to report ME (Farag et al., 2017)		71 Emergency Department (ED) nurse 71 of 158 surveys returned.		error has high pt harm potential 54.9% stated very likely to report if error was caught and corrected before reaching pt (near miss) ED unit safety climate has no positive correlation on reporting RN exp vs willingness to report is negative ($r = -0.25$, $p = .03$) Error feedback corrective with willingness to report ($r = 0.25$, $p = .03$)	Limitation: small sample size. Might not be generalizable to other settings. Data collected was self-reported, bias cannot be excluded. Notes: Clear expectation timely feedback, and non-punitive attitude from nurse manager has positive impact on nurses' willingness to report.
To explore nurses' attitude and perception of barrier to report MAE; and to understand nurses' view about error report. (Yung et al., 2016)	Cross-sectional study design Convenience sample	Large teaching hospital (>2900 beds) Inclusion: nurses from ICU, Medical, surgical, Pediatric and mixed wards Exclusion: nurses from OR, psychiatric wards, outpatient.	3 parts questionnaires: 10 items (Likert scale 1-4) on nurses' attitude toward MA error reporting; 22 (Likert scale 1-4) items on what nurses view as barriers; 1-8 items aimed on fear of the consequences; 9-18 items targeted on lack of awareness of report; 19-22 aimed on the negative impacts of administrator attitude;	Nursing staff: M age=32.8 Average 9.7 experience (SD=6.2). 87.7% w/ BSN, ICU nurse=45.5%. Nurse leaders: M age=48.5 (SD 6.1) Average 26.5 exp (SD 6.2); >50% w/ MS or PhD; 35.3%=mixed ward.	Limitation: Might not be generalizable to other settings. Notes: nurse leaders need to train staff on how to report and serve as a role model to encourage reporting. Again, safety culture is important to

Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample & setting	Measurements/operational	Findings	Conclusions & Notes
		340 questionnaires' sent out. 306 responded. Divvied into two group: nurse leader (51) and nursing staff (255).	last part is multiple choice encouraged participants to reflect on a known MAE. Content validity is validated by five experts. Reliability: alpha =0.81 and 0.86 for the barriers items.	<p>Nursing staff ($M=2.75$, $SD=0.34$) perceived reporting barrier ↑ nurse leader ($M = 2.61$, $SD=0.35$).</p> <p>Nursing staff most negative attitude: if there was no harm to pt, it is not necessary to report.</p> <p>Common barrier: fear of consequence ($M = 3.18$, $SD=0.48$), followed by lack of awareness about reporting.</p> <p>Highest ranked three items were 1) fear of being dis-trusted by pt and family ($M = 3.31$, $SD=0.54$); 2) fear error being taken as a negative performance by administrator; 3) fear of causing pt-nurse dispute ($M = 3.30$; $SD=0.35$).</p> <p>83% nurses felt self-recrimination after reporting.</p>	<p>promote voluntary reporting.</p> <p>90% of Medication Error Report (MER) done orally or informally to head nurse, did head nurse encourage staff to report?</p>

Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample & setting	Measurements/operational	Findings	Conclusions & Notes
				90% ME filed informally or orally to head nurse. Official reporting only 19%.	
To explore association of nurses' attitude and intention of MAE vs actual reporting (Hung, Chu, Lee, & Hsiao, 2016)	Cross-section w/ self-administered questionnaires	1379 beds regional teaching hospital in Taiwan Nurses in general wards & ICU (25 units) 596 nurses invited, 548 (92%) returned survey. Inclusion: >3month experience in the participation units Exclusion: directors and managers	Nurses' attitude and intention to report is measure by scale in Chinese used in previous studies. Participants recalled their MAE experience over previous 3 months. Announcement made in meetings 2 days prior questionnaire were sent. 9/2013-11/2013 data collection period	Average experience as nurse: 4.5 years (SD=4.0); employment: 3.9 years (SD 3.7); average # of MAE officially reported in past 3 months:0.4 (SD 1.0). 87.9% nurses were Novice & Advanced beginner Nurses' attitude ($b = 0.41$) and coworkers' attitude ($b = 0.29$) positively affect nurses' intention to report No significant finding between intention to report & actual reporting ($b = 0.07$)	Limitation: Generalizability Conclusion: intent to report do not equate to actual reporting Note: Lack of awareness of ME hinder reporting. A supportive unit environment promotes reporting. This study did not find any significant association among nurses' manager attitude with nurses reporting.
To understand ME reporting barriers and facilitators.	Descriptive study Questionnaires.	Teaching hospital in Iran.	Questionnaires based on Haddon matrix.	Nurse who had ME w/o pt harm reported <1/4 of errors;	ME reporting rate is low. Study concluded that a reliable environment that

Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample & setting	Measurements/operational	Findings	Conclusions & Notes
(Bayazidi et al., 2012)	Content validity of the questionnaires were assessed by 10 nursing faculty members. Reliability was tested by 20 nurse to take questionnaires twice within one week interval ($r=0.83-0.90$)	733 nurses who are directly involved in Medication Administration (MA). Exclusion: unwilling to participate in study	1 st part collected demographic and social information of the nurses. 2 nd part consisted 3 medication reporting rate items, 8 barriers of reporting items, and 7 facilitators of reporting items.	major ME w/ pt harm reported <1/2 of errors. Nurses perceived biggest barrier: individual blame, consequence of error, and fear of reprimand and punishment. Other barriers: “no need to report if no harm to pt,” “ME perceived as unimportant by nurses,” “ME reports take too long to complete.” Facilitators to reports: “anonymous reporting system,” “a perceived benefit of reporting” and “eliminating the fearful atmosphere in the organization”	nurse feel safe to report will increase ME reporting. Limitation: participants might not provide accurate answer to questionnaires. Notes: ME w/o pt harm is less likely to be reported. Need to educate and emphasize on the systemic impact of any “near miss” and no harm ME, it can help to improve the safety system wide. Interested to know if there is any correlation among years of rn exp. vs error reported.
To understand gap in perception of Safety Patient Initiative (SPI) between in frontline nurses’ and nurse managers’.	Pilot survey	20 SPI organization. SPI: organizational quality initiative made changes in clinical processes w/ core focus of communication, team work,	9 questions about SPI program elements and success factors, Likert scale was used. 16 questions about impact and sustainability of SPI program.	Frontline staff rated “working w/ a partner organization to share learning” as more important than senior managers ($t = -2.749, p = 0.006$)	Varying perceptions on safe program among staff at different level. Limitation: social desirability bias, frontline staff might not answer truthfully

Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample & setting	Measurements/operational	Findings	Conclusions & Notes
(Parand et al., 2011)		<p>leadership and safety culture</p> <p>Systematic sampling: Senior executive leads, the principal SPI program coordinator, operational leads in each of the clinical area and other staff who were involved w/I the program.</p> <p>635 survey response were obtained (52%)</p> <p>n=133 frontline staff n=442 senior managers</p>		<p>Senior manager rated “availability of early adopters to lead the testing of change” ($t = -2.457, p = 0.014$) and “support from nurse for the SPI program” ($t = 3.572, p = 0.000$) more than frontline staff.</p> <p>No significant difference among two group on manager led or frontline approach ($t = 2.292, P = 0.023$)</p>	<p>about their managers and organization</p> <p>Notes: although this is not directly surveyed on medication error, it is still significant finding to know the difference in perception among leaders and staff nurses regarding quality initiative.</p> <p>Sometimes leaders might not be best to deliver clear expectation and whole concept to staff. “Teach back” needed to ensure staff fully understand medication safety.</p> <p>Frontline staff need to be included in developing and implementing medication safety program.</p>

Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample & setting	Measurements/operational	Findings	Conclusions & Notes
To review personal and system contributing factors to ME. (Brady et al., 2009)	Literature review Peer reviewed & English 1998-2007	26 qualitative & quantitative studies included. All over the world.	96 papers retrieved and appraised for relevance, methodological rigors, and trustworthiness.	<p>Factors concluded: medication reconciliation, type of drug distribution system, quality of prescriptions, deviation from procedure (distraction, excessive workloads, and nurses knowledge of medications)</p> <p>In nurses' knowledge factor, one study found 265 drugs errors (both minor and major) were under detected due to nurses not being aware a mistaken had occurred.</p> <p>In error reporting, a study found that 50% of nurses did not report ME due to fear of negative repercussion.</p> <p>Nurses' interpretation of ME identified as one of factor obstruct reporting.</p>	<p>Conclusion: findings were diverse: both individual and system issues.</p> <p>Limitation: Studies inclusion criteria were not detailed.</p> <p>Similar findings as previous studies that nurses' knowledge to recognize error; non punitive approach, clear definition of ME is essential to support voluntary report.</p>

Note: BSN = Bachelor of Science in Nursing; ICU = Intensive Care Unit; M = Mean; MA = Medication Administration; MAE = Medication Administration Error; ME = Medication Error; MER= Medication Error Report; OR = Operation Room; pt = Patient; yrs = Years;

Table 2

Medication Safety Program in Hospitals

Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample & setting	Measurements/operational	Findings	Conclusions; study limitations & Notes
To evaluate effectiveness of medication error (ME) reduction intervention programs in the hospitals (Berdot et al., 2016)	Systemic review and meta-analysis RCT, interrupted time-series studies, non-RCT, and controlled before and after studies were included.	5312 records identified from 1975-2014. 7 studies included. 5 RCT (included a crossover trial), 2 non RCT.	2 of authors independently assessed studies for eligibility & risk of bias, data extraction. Studies focus on administration error (excluded wrong time errors): total errors relative to total opportunities of error. Interventions were training related: 4 dedicated medication RNs, interactive CD-ROM program, simulation based learning, pharmacist-led training program, and 3 technology related	No difference in administration error; 2 studies favor the intervention group (crossover studies showed decreased in error rate). 1 study used simulation based training vs. traditional training; another study used pharmacist led the training that combined lecture, practice based education and posters. 2 studies favor the control group. One used dedicated medication nurse and another study used interactive CD-ROM education material. 3 technology related studies showed no difference in reduce medication administration error.	All studies subject to bias due to lack of blinding. High heterogeneity $I^2 = 94.9\%$ Note: simulation based learning is more effective than traditional didactic lecture learning. Hospital is moving toward online learning on mandatory education/training to save money. Current hospital is using barcode scanning as one of the safety medication intervention. How to effectively increase nurses' knowledge & understanding medication error definition.
To identify effective	Systematic review	6 RCTs & 7 CTs	PICOS method (Participants, intervention, comparison,	Medication use technology: BCMA &	Limitation: bias from sample studies setting

Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample & setting	Measurements/operational	Findings	Conclusions; study limitations & Notes
intervention to reduce ME (Keers et al., 2014)	Studies between 1985 and November 2013 Inclusion: RCT and Controlled Trials (CT)	medication use technology n=4 nurses education and training n=3 change practice in anesthesia n=2 ward system change n=4	outcomes and study design) was used Two authors independently abstracted and met to reach consensus on core details, study backgrounds and outcome measures Study authors were contracted for additional data	CPOE ↓MAE; smart infusion pump ↓ IV related MAE; Nurse education and training: nurses undergo lectures and practice-based training program reported positive in ↓ MAE. Self-directed educational CD ROM program has no significant impact. Simulated based learning and clinical pharmacist-led training program were more effective than standard practices. 2 nurse double check ↑ medication safety	might alter outcome and cause bias in this study. Notes: significant improvement in MAE rate with nurse's education and training.
To identify best practice in incident reporting feedback. (Benn et al., 2009)	Systemic review & semi structured interviews Healthcare system all over the world.	23 reporting system from healthcare system all over the world. 19 subject-matter expert interview to identified requirements of safety feedback framework.	Inclusion: articles w/ incident monitoring, theoretical and practical issues concerning organization learning, use of feedback. Exclusion: topic analyzed specific type of incidents, description of taxonomies for categorizing incidents, human factors analysis technique and legal issues.	Timely corrective action, broad information dissemination and adequate feedback encourages reporting. Expert panel identified 15 requirements to provide feedback to frontline staff, as well	Limitation: the operation details of feedback practice was referenced based on literature at the time, need to be evaluated systematically. Notes: to develop strategies/policy identify medication error definition, details

Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample & setting	Measurements/operational	Findings	Conclusions; study limitations & Notes
			2134 record identified, 29 articles selected out of 193. Expert interview identified 15 requirements to design effective safety feedback framework.	<p>as the rationales of each requirement.</p> <p>Closing the loop timely is essential to promote voluntary reporting.</p> <p>Feedback should focus on systematic approach, rather than individual blame; leadership support & commitment for pt safety culture.</p> <p>Framework SAIFIR was proposed.</p>	<p>the process of incident reporting. To reduce staff's concern of individual punishment.</p> <p>Adapt parts of the 15 requirements to provide feedback of medication error.</p> <p>Adapt SAIFIR framework.</p> <p>Current incident reporting system do not require sign in, individual can remain anonymous, unable to provide instant feedback. Maybe send an email to staff acknowledging receipt of reporting?</p>
To compare similarities and differences in two units' use of one incident reporting system and factors account for differences (Hewitt et al., 2016)	Comparative case study Semi-structured interview 2 units: General Internal Medicine (GIM) & Obstetrics and Neonatology (OBS/NEO)	40 GIM staff (11 physicians, 5 nurse leaders, 15 bedside nurses, 3 pharmacy, 3 physiotherapist, 3 nursing support) interviewed 45 OBS/NEO staff interviewed (8 physicians, 15 nurse leaders, 15 bedside nurses, 4	Analysis of each unit done separately then engaged in comparison, followed Miles and Huberman's recommendation Interviews digitally record and transcribed 2 researchers agreed on interview themes and codes.	Same Incident reporting system (IRS) in 2 units, different process at each stage GIM: Incident reported by nurses, outcome bases (fall & ME); individual manager review & investigation; feedback to individual	Limitation: OBS/NEO unit staff had more experience w/ Incident reporting process; GIM staff had less experience. Notes: IRS is tool for front line staff to report any out of norm events to their leaders, however, staff training necessary on not just instrumental process,

Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample & setting	Measurements/operational	Findings	Conclusions; study limitations & Notes
		midwives, 4 (respiratory therapy)		<p>nurses; and at staff meeting</p> <p>OBS/NEO: Team approach in reporting; outcome/near misses reported; leader and multidisciplinary committee review; system focus; feedback to all staff at meetings, bi-annual newsletter, occasional reporter participation in Quality Assurance meeting</p> <p>Factors account for difference</p> <p>1. Legal GIM: lower threat, ↓reporting OBS/NEO: higher threat ↑ reporting</p> <p>2. Introduction IRS GIM: Top down, focus on logistics of reporting. leaders not participate in corporate planning meeting OBS/NEO: bottom up; leaders proactively participate in planning. staff</p>	<p>also reasons of reporting. When staff understand the “WHY” behind a process, it drives compliance and practice.</p> <p>Leaders play a key role in promoting appropriate usage of IRS.</p>

Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample & setting	Measurements/operational	Findings	Conclusions; study limitations & Notes
				<p>trained on reason to report</p> <p>3. Inter-professional training GIM: minimal OBS/NEO: more, focus on safety practices w/ OBS specific predecessor.</p>	
<p>To examine current medication management program in two hospitals, and to understand current nursing students' medication safety knowledge</p> <p>(Adhikari et al., 2014)</p>	<p>Direct observation & interview</p> <p>Study approved by local ethical committee</p> <p>qualitative analytic method: interpret and analyze transcription</p>	<p>Two hospital wards in two different hospitals and three local Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Scotland.</p> <p>July and October 2012</p> <p>Interview: charge nurses = 4 and RN = 3</p>	<p>Observer shadowed each nurse, pharmacist and pharmacy technician for about one hour, followed by a 20-30 min discussion.</p> <p>Interviews were conducted with registered nurses.</p> <p>Final year nursing students in three HEIs using two focus group discussions (n = 11; n = 8) and one peer-discussion (n = 2).</p>	<p>Authors concluded traditional 5 rights administration technique is not enough, and a multidisciplinary approach is critical to maintain medication safety from medication reconciliation to medication administration.</p> <p>Authors concluded that new RNs need extensive pharmacology knowledge and need training on systemic process in medication safety.</p>	<p>Limitation: snap shot of medication practice. Not generalizable to other setting. Article did not mention who conduct the analyzation of transcription, no mention of interpersonal validity.</p> <p>Notes: agreed w/ study that solely rely 5 rights to prevent ME is not realistic, medication error can happen at any stage. If nurse do not have pharmacology knowledge, they might not fully understand the rationale of medication, and end up simply carry out order.</p> <p>Recently a ME occurred when pharmacist transcribed the</p>

Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample & setting	Measurements/operational	Findings	Conclusions; study limitations & Notes
					medication (albuterol Q6 started at 1300 was entered at albuterol once a day at 1300) frequently inaccurately, 4 shift of different RNs (new grad) took care of the pt did not notice the error. Error was caught by an experience RN.
To reduce harmful ADEs by revision of Medication safety process (McClead et al., 2014)	Quasi-experimental time series quality improvement initiative No intervention involved a comparison of therapy, and pt are not subjected to randomization. No IRB needed.	NCH, 450 beds freestanding children's hospital in Columbus, Ohio	Revision of independent double check process for high-risk medication; implementation of wireless communication system to allow nurse to identify colleague for double check process; additional smart pumps to promote accessibility for drug programing; rigorous unit-based audits of 5 rights MA; implementation of BCMA. ADE huddles with front line staff to learn how and why the error occurred. Just culture-Zero hero initiative.	Non harmful ADE peaked in 2010 with the zero hero initiative. By 2011, ADE rate dropped by 52%, from a mean of 0.17 to 0.08 per 1000 doses dispended ($p < .001$). ADE bundle audit achieved 100% in 5 rights and double check, smart pump medication library audit. 76.5% reduction in the rate of harmful ADEs during study period.	Author believed the internal quality collaborative model, focus on medication management failure models, and reliable use of ADE buddle, evolution of a safety culture contributed to medication error reporting. Notes: Double check process of high risk medication already in placed in current hospital and did not find any gap as of today. The smart pumps had been implemented, new hire need more training. Audit and observation of medication administration enhance medication guideline compliance. Safe

Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample & setting	Measurements/operational	Findings	Conclusions; study limitations & Notes
					practice can be trained, even staff might act differently when being observed, however it is a good way to reinforce the importance of following guidelines. Will look in to BCMA compliance rate. RN high turn around at current hospital is an issue to sustain safety program.
To evaluate effectiveness of five-point management strategies in reducing ME:	Quasi-experiment; Outcome were measured using quantitative and qualitative approaches	31 units of a large general hospital in southeast China from 2008-2012	5 safety committee members conducted observation quarterly on 1) rate of accurate compliance with medication policies and procedures; 2) success rate of MA procedures; 3) # of complaints related to nursing MA	100% participation rate	Nurses' awareness of medication safety, MA skill & pt satisfaction improved.
(Xu et al., 2014)	Intervention: training program; optimizing medication policies; refining drug classification; enhancing the safety process for IV meds; supervising process of MA	2008-2010 pre-intervention assessment; 2011-2012 implementation period	Data abstraction on frequency of ME, rate of nurses-initiated ME reports;	pre-intervention: common errors omission of medication & wrong pt;	Limitation: lack of concurrent comparison group over a 4 yr. study period.
	Rate of accurate compliance with medication P&P; success rate of MA procedures; # of		5 IP pt surveyed on satisfaction w/ medication management;	post-intervention: common error omission and wrong preparation	Observation sample not randomized.
			9 head RN and 6 senior nurse practitioner gave feedback via semi structure interviews at end of 4 th year	# of nurse initiated ME report/total ME improve from 77.1% (101/131) to 95.1% (58/61)	Staff might act differently if known being observed;
				rate of compliance w/ P&P increased from 86.7%(645/744) to 97.5% (725/744)	Notes: medication policies were incorporated into training where a standardized definition ↑nursing knowledge-

Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample & setting	Measurements/operational	Findings	Conclusions; study limitations & Notes
	complaints related to nursing medication administration; frequency of ME, rate of nurses-initiated ME reports; IP satisfaction w/ medication management;				<p>>↑nurse initiated reporting due to change to computerized reporting system and incentive with reporting.</p> <p>Direct observation can detect errors that nurses might not aware of, help to reinforce five rights administration practice.</p> <p>Encouragement vs punishment helps to promote reporting. Might not able to have financial incentive like this study.</p>
To understand the barriers to MER in hospitals, and encourage MER (Hartnell et al., 2012)	Qualitative Focus group (pharmacist, physician and nurses) in depth interview	Four community hospitals in Nova Scotia, Canada 7 pharmacists, 9 physicians and 14 nurses participated	Safety culture theory used in the study Audio tapes were transcribed verbatim and analyzed Transcript was coded initially and re-coded a few days for recode reliability Only one person ducted data collection and analysis.	Barriers Reporter burden: extra time and work to report Professional identified: do not want to tell on coworkers Information gap: lack of definition or standards for reporting Organization factor: ineffective reporting system; reporting is	Limitation: small sample size, subjective to individual bias on MER. Notes: DNP hospital is similar size to the study hospitals. Common findings were disconnection between managers and front line nurses. Incident report findings need to circle back to front line staff. Important to have a standardize guideline for staff to refer to for

Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample & setting	Measurements/operational	Findings	Conclusions; study limitations & Notes
				<p>someone else reasonability; lack of understanding the benefits of reporting</p> <p>Fear: fear of reprisal from manager; fear of lawsuits</p> <p>Facilitators identified among all four hospitals were</p> <p>1.Reduce reporting burden: easier reporting system; 2. Bridge gap of MAE reporting and feedback; 3. Educate on standardized reporting guideline</p>	what to report and when to report.

Note: ADE = Adverse Drug Event; BCMA = Bar-coded medication administration; ED = Emergency Department; IEC = Institutional Ethics Committee; ICU = Intensive Care Unit; IP = Inpatient; IV = Intravenous; MA= Medication Administration; MAE = Medication Administration Error; ME = Medication Error; MER = Medication Error Report; Pt = Patient; P&P = Policy & Procedure; RCT = Randomized controlled trials; SAIFIR = Safety Action and Information Feedback from Incident reporting.